

Love Food, Hate Waste?

Understand the impacts of donating your surplus food

Food loss and waste (FLW) creates greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and exacerbates biodiversity loss by driving unnecessary resource extraction and land use. Through the [CULTIVATE](#) project, Sharing Solutions is working with a range of food actors - including retailers - across Europe to reduce FLW and optimise sustainability impacts. Globally, around a third of all food produced is lost or wasted creating significant negative impacts on people and the planet. In Europe, annual FLW is **132 kg per capita** across the supply chain ([EEA, 2025](#)).

The retail and distribution sector represents a critical leverage point for action, not only contributing 8% of the overall FLW figure in Europe, but also having close connections upstream to producers and processors and downstream to households and food service operations.

Efforts to increase the **redistribution of surplus food from retailers** to those who need it have significantly increased over the past decade, with inspirational organisations like [Boroume](#) and [FoodCloud](#) creating social and technical innovations to scale up this practice. However, the impacts created from this redistribution are rarely known by donors, recipients, policy makers or funders.

[Sharing Solutions](#) has supported a range of food sharing initiatives (FSIs), including community gardens, community kitchens and surplus food redistribution activities, to identify, understand and optimise their sustainability contributions to UPU food systems through its bespoke sustainability impacts tool - [The Toolshed](#). This work is showcased on the [Talent Garden](#) and includes documenting the social, economic, environmental and governance impacts created by surplus food donations.

A range of sustainability metrics have been developed to inform retailers about the kinds of impacts that can be created if food is donated through FSIs to communities.

[FoodCloud](#) - A Cultivate consortium partner & Sharing Solutions client, serving meals made from donated food

[Boroume](#) - A Cultivate consortium partner & Sharing Solutions client, redistributing surplus food

Sustainability impact metrics

A sustainability impact framework has been established that outlines the **impacts that redirecting food from disposal through food sharing creates within Europe**, combining data from FSIs and international [research](#). These impacts are presented per **1 kg of edible surplus food redistributed to communities**:

Environmental	✓	3.2 kg CO ₂ e emissions avoided	
	✓	8,500 litres of water preserved	
	✓	€3.51 in avoided food value loss	
	✓	€0.16 avoided waste management costs	
Economic	✓	€3.51 in avoided food value loss	
	✓	€0.16 avoided waste management costs	
Social	✓	2 meals provided	
	✓	1134 kcal	

These figures are averages and provide a conservative cross-category estimate suitable for reporting where product-level data is unavailable. Below is one example from a supermarket.

Case Study: Impact from surplus food donations

A leading Greek retailer **demonstrated the power of food redistribution** by donating **2,167 tonnes of surplus food** through 122 stores by collaborating with a Food Sharing Initiative (FSI) partner, [Boroume](#).

This surplus was transformed into measurable benefits:

- **Environmental:** Saved **18.17 million m³ of water** (7,000+ Olympic pools) and prevented **6,934 tonnes of CO₂e emissions**, the equivalent of removing 1,500 cars from the road.
- **Social:** Provided food for **3.7 million meals**, feeding the equivalent of the entire population of Athens while fostering community cohesion and reducing loneliness.
- **Economic:** Generated a **€6.54 million gross saving**, comprising €6.20 million in avoided production and €335,885 in direct waste savings.

Reducing Waste - Creating Space

Sharing Solutions helps food retailers across Europe, from independent retailers to large supermarkets, to identify, understand, and communicate the full sustainability impacts of donating food with our [Sustainability Impact Assessment Framework](#). This ensures visibility is given to the social, environmental, and economic footprint of all food retail business donations, giving retailers space to focus on their goals and community groups operational capacity to better meet the needs of their participants.

- ✓ **What we do:** We support the measurement of social, environmental, and economic impacts from surplus food redistribution, connecting these to the sustainable development goals. We disseminate best practice around surplus food donation and provide guidance on regulatory requirements.
- ✓ **How it helps:** Understanding impact strengthens CSR activities and reporting, helps to engage staff in practical actions and supports businesses to meet sustainability targets. Using our supports helps identify and mitigate benefits and mitigates risks around donation and aligns with ESG and CSRD reporting practices.
- ✓ **Who is it for:** Our supports are designed for all food retailers, whether wholesalers, independent food businesses, restaurants or supermarkets.

Get started: Email: info@sharingsolutions.eu to connect with Sharing Solutions

Other supports from CULTIVATE include:

- [The Menu of Good Governance](#)
Signposts best practices and regulatory frameworks for surplus food redistribution
- [The Library of Citizen Engagement](#)
Inspires chefs and other food citizens to engage in food sharing through a library of games and tools
- [The Food Sharing Calculator](#)
Supports the identification of costs, benefits and impacts from redistributed surplus, and food sharing more broadly
- [The Food Sharing Map](#)
Locates FSIs across your city, helping you to connect with organisations that can ensure Food Loss and Waste minimisation.